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Highly stable Pt/CoAl₂O₄ catalysts in Aqueous-Phase Reforming of glycerol

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32 **Abstract**

33 Pt/CoAl₂O₄ catalysts with small amounts of Pt (0.3 and 1 wt.%) were prepared by wet impregnation
34 of platinum on cobalt aluminate (mole ratio Co/Al=0.625). These catalysts were compared with
35 monometallic Pt/alumina and cobalt aluminate counterparts. The physicochemical characteristics of
36 the obtained materials were thoroughly analysed. The catalytic performance of the prepared assays
37 was investigated in the Aqueous-Phase Reforming (APR) of glycerol for up to 100 h TOS, and in
38 liquid phase Water-Gas Shift (WGS). It was concluded that the addition of Pt to cobalt aluminate
39 resulted in a synergistic effect that promoted the reduction of both Pt and Co species, as well as cobalt
40 dispersion, what increased the amount of exposed metallic sites. These effects were, however,
41 sensitive to the amount of Pt loaded. The glycerol APR activity of bimetallic catalysts was very stable
42 over 100 h TOS with conversion values above 99%. Conversion to gas was also above 95% during
43 the whole operation. Contrarily, the counterpart monometallic catalysts suffered noticeable
44 deactivation at above 70 h TOS. Also, WGS activity of bimetallic assays was higher than the
45 monometallic counterparts. Addition of Pt to cobalt aluminate lowered selectivity to hydrogen, due
46 to a higher CO hydrogenation activity. Examination of the spent catalysts showed better textural
47 stability of the bimetallic samples, as well as much lesser formation of carbonaceous surface deposits.
48 Nevertheless, oxidation and leaching of cobalt remains as the main drawback of bimetallic catalysts
49 to be used in APR.

50

51 **1. Introduction**

52 The environmental concern related to the use of fossil fuels has driven much interest in renewable
53 energy production from biomass. In particular, glycerol is an inexpensive and readily available sub-
54 product of biodiesel units that can be used to produce hydrogen [1]. Due to its high functionalization,
55 glycerol presents high chemical reactivity that allows its valorisation by, among other routes,
56 oxidation, reforming, hydrodeoxygenation, and hydrogenation [2].

57 Hydrogen produced from biomass is an alternative to traditional fossil feedstocks and can be therefore
58 part of a low-carbon energy system. Aqueous-Phase Reforming (APR) is one of the most
59 straightforward methods for the valorisation of glycerol which enables the production of hydrogen or
60 alkanes by tuning the catalysts properties and operation conditions [3] (Figure 1). APR can be used
61 for a sort of oxygenated substrates, as oxygenated hydrocarbons feedstock from biomass (sugars and
62 polyols), Fisher-Tropsch residuals [4] or food industry residuals [5,6]. The APR process is
63 advantageous over conventional steam reforming, since it works at lower temperatures and somewhat
64 higher pressures, which eliminates the necessity to vaporize the feedstream, with the energy-saving
65 advantage thereof. Typically, APR process is conducted in the 220-260 °C range and at moderate
66 pressure (30-50 bar) in order to keep the reaction mixture in liquid phase. In addition, this low
67 working temperatures shift the WGS equilibrium, so an hydrogen stream with low CO concentration
68 can be obtained in a single reactor.

69 APR of an oxygenated hydrocarbon proceeds through a complex reaction network, and ideally, results
70 in H₂ and CO₂ mixture. In the case of glycerol APR over transition metal catalysts, two main paths
71 have been proposed [7] (Figure 1): through Path I, promoted by metallic sites, hydroxyl group at
72 primary carbon is dehydrogenated to give glyceraldehyde, which rapidly undergoes C-C scission
73 resulting in ethylene glycol and CO. Ethylene glycol undergoes further dehydrogenation and C-C
74 cleavage, while CO can react via Water-Gas Shift giving additional hydrogen [8]. WGS is considered
75 the rate-limiting step in APR [9].

76 **FIGURE 1**

77 Overall, the glycerol APR (reaction 1) gives, ideally, 7 moles of hydrogen per mole of converted
78 glycerol.

80

81 Through Path II, glycerol is firstly dehydrated to hydroxyacetone, which subsequently can be
82 hydrogenated to propylene glycol. The resulting intermediates are further converted through a

83 complex reaction system that involves hydrogenation/dehydrogenation/dehydration/hydrogenolysis
84 reactions. Path II is promoted by acidic supports, which enables high yields to alkanes, as well as
85 intermediate liquid oxygenates. In order to maximize hydrogen yield, Path I should be favoured, what
86 would require mainly metallic sites in the catalyst. Thus, an effective catalyst should be active for C-
87 C and C-H bond cleavage, as well as for WGS reaction [10], which is a key reaction to convert to
88 CO₂ the primary product CO from decarbonylation, and simultaneously produce additional hydrogen.
89 In addition, in order to achieve high hydrogen yield, catalyst should be inactive in C-O bond cleavage
90 and avoid hydrogen consumption in parallel hydrogenation reactions, which give rise to light alkanes
91 and liquid intermediates [11]. Among the suitable metals for APR, Pt has outstanding performance
92 due to its high C-C scission and WGS activity. However, transition metals such as Ni or Co have
93 been also investigated [12,13]. Metal combinations of Pt, Co and others have been proposed in order
94 to enhance the catalyst performance in many reactions [14-16]. Dietrich et al. [11] reported that the
95 addition of Co to Pt (molar ratio 1:1) increased glycerol conversion, H₂ and CO₂ production by a
96 factor of 2 for the APR of glycerol. Dosso et al. [17] showed a beneficial effect upon addition of Ni
97 or Co to Pt catalysts, evidenced as an increase in the yield to hydrogen, improved stability, and
98 lessening of coke deposits.

99 APR is performed under harsh hydrothermal conditions, therefore, catalyst deactivation is commonly
100 an issue. The main causes vary depending on the active metal, the support and the type of reactor
101 used [18]. Active metal leaching (especially transition metals) [19-21] and/or oxidation and
102 deposition of graphitic carbon [22] have been reported as main causes.

103 In our previous work [7] we prepared cobalt aluminate spinel derived catalysts for APR of glycerol
104 with relatively high Co dispersion. The most active assay (bulk Co/Al molar ratio of 0.625) converted
105 88% of glycerol with 22% conversion to gas, at 235 °C/3.5 MPa, and produced 231 μmol_{H₂}/g_{cat}·min,
106 with 60% H₂ in the gas stream. However, catalyst stability was compromised. In order to solve this
107 aspect and enhance the space-time yields, in this work different amounts of platinum were
108 impregnated on cobalt aluminate. The catalytic performance was tested in the Aqueous-Phase
109 Reforming of 10 wt.% glycerol/water synthetic mixtures, and the obtained results discussed in terms
110 of the structure-activity-stability relationship. For comparison, 0.3Pt/γ-alumina and bare cobalt
111 aluminate samples were also tested.

112 **2. Experimental Section**

113 **2.1. Catalysts preparation**

114 Cobalt aluminate spinel (nominal Co/Al mole ratio=0.625) was prepared by coprecipitation, as
115 reported elsewhere [7]. Briefly, proper amounts of aqueous solutions of cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate

116 and aluminium(III) nitrate nonahydrate were coprecipitated with sodium carbonate at pH 10. The
117 resulting suspension was aged at room temperature for 24 h, filtered, washed several times with de-
118 ionized water, dried at 110 °C for 17 h and calcined in a muffle furnace at 500 °C (heating rate 5
119 °C/min) for 5 h in a static air atmosphere. This sample was abbreviated CoAl.

120 Platinum (with nominal contents of 0.3 and 1 wt.%) was added to the cobalt aluminate spinel (CoAl)
121 by wet impregnation method, using tetraammineplatinum(II) nitrate (Alfa Aesar, % 99.99) as the
122 metal precursor, dissolved in deionized water. After impregnation, the solids were dried at 110 °C for
123 17 h and finally, calcined in air at 350 °C in a muffle furnace (heating rate 5 °C/min) for 3 h. These
124 samples were abbreviated xPt/CoAl, where x denotes the nominal wt.% of Pt. For comparative
125 purposes, γ -Al₂O₃-supported Pt catalyst was prepared by the same procedure (abbreviated 0.3Pt/Al).
126 γ -alumina was prepared by calcination of aluminium(III) nitrate nonahydrate in air, at 500 °C for 4 h
127 (heating rate 5 °C/min).

128 **2.2. Catalysts characterization**

129 ICP-AES (Perkin Elmer, Optima 8300) was used to analyse the metal concentration in the prepared
130 catalysts and also in the liquid phase products. Prior to analysis, solid samples were digested in *aqua*
131 *regia* (volume ratio HCl/HNO₃: 3/1) in closed containers for 24 h at 100 °C. Reaction exhaust liquid
132 samples were previously diluted in nitric acid (ratio 1:50). Textural properties of the solids were
133 measured by nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K, carried out into Micromeritics TriStar
134 II 3020 apparatus. Prior to the adsorption, samples were outgassed at 300 °C for 10 h. Specific surface
135 area was calculated by BET method, while the pore size distribution was determined with BJH
136 formalism. The crystalline structure of the samples was analysed by XRD (PANalytical X'pert PRO
137 diffractometer, using CuK α radiation, λ =1.5406 Å). Each sample was scanned from 10 to 90° (2 θ),
138 with a step size of 0.026° (2 θ) and a counting time of 2 s. Phase identification was done by comparison
139 of the obtained spectra and the PDF database. Scherrer equation was used to calculate the crystallite
140 average size.

141 ²⁷Al Solid State NMR measurements were performed on a 9.4 T Bruker AVANCE III 400
142 spectrometer operating at resonance frequencies of 104.26 MHz for ²⁷Al. Chemical shifts were
143 referenced externally to the AlCl₃ aqueous solution at 0 ppm. The spectra were acquired at a spinning
144 frequency of 60 kHz employing a PH MASDVT400W BL 1.3mm ultrafast probe head. A single pulse
145 of 0.3 microseconds duration was applied and a recycle delay of 0.2 s and 36,000 scans were used.

146 Temperature programmed reduction (H₂-TPR) was carried out using an Micromeritics AutoChem
147 2920 apparatus, equipped with thermal conductivity detector (TCD). About 50 mg of sample was
148 heated in He stream at 500 °C for 1 h (heating rate 10 °C/min) to clean the sample. Then, the

149 temperature was lowered to ambient temperature into Ar flow. Finally, in 5% H₂-Ar flow, the
150 temperature was ramped to 950 °C at 10 °C/min heating rate, and hold for 1 h.

151 H₂ chemisorption was carried out in a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 equipment in dynamic mode,
152 at 40 °C. Discrimination between Pt and Co metallic sites, was effected by applying two consecutive
153 chemisorption pulses. Previously, surface was cleaned into He flow at 500 °C. First, catalysts was
154 reduced at 250 °C in 5%H₂/Ar flow (heating rate 10 °C/min, hold 1 h), and cooled down to 40 °C in
155 Ar flow. Pulses of 5%H₂/Ar were injected (loop volume 0.5312 mL) until peaks had equal area.
156 Secondly, the sample was heated in 5%H₂/Ar flow to 600 °C (heating rate 10 °C/min, hold 1 h), and
157 evacuated in Ar for 15 min. Temperature was cooled down to 40 °C into Ar flow and a new pulse
158 chemisorption was completed. Hydrogen uptake by the sample reduced at 250 °C was assigned to Pt
159 sites, while uptake after reduction at 600 °C was assigned to both Pt and Co sites. H/Me (Me=Pt, Co)
160 stoichiometry of 1/1 was assumed.

161 Total surface acidity was measured by weighing the chemisorbed ammonia by thermogravimetry
162 (Setaram Setsys). About 80 mg of sample was placed in an alumina crucible, and in-situ reduced at
163 600 °C for 2 h under 50 mL/min 5%H₂/Ar flow. The sample was then cooled down to 50 °C under 50
164 mL/min 5%H₂/Ar flow. Thereafter, the flow was switched to 10%NH₃/He (16 mL/min) for 1 h.
165 Finally, the ammonia flow was stopped while 5%H₂/Ar (50 mL/min) was circulated through the
166 reactor for 1 h in order to desorb the physisorbed ammonia. The eventual mass gain of the sample
167 corresponded to the chemisorbed ammonia.

168 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to detect the electronic state of Pt, Co and Al in
169 the prepared samples. The spectra were measured using a SPECS spectrometer with Phoibos 150
170 1DDLD analyser and monochromatized Al K α (1486.7 eV) X-ray radiation in ultrahigh vacuum.
171 Binding energies were calibrated by taking C 1s peak (284.6 eV) of adventitious carbon as reference.
172 The peaks were deconvoluted after Shirley background subtraction, using a mixed Gaussian-
173 Lorentzian function and concentrations were calculated by correcting the values with relative atomic
174 sensitivity factors (Scofield).

175 Raman analysis of the spent catalysts was carried out in a Renishaw InVia Raman spectrometer
176 coupled to a Leica DMLM microscope, using a laser of 514 nm (ion-argon laser, Modu-Laser). The
177 power density of the laser beam was reduced in order to avoid the photo-decomposition of the
178 samples. In order to improve the signal to noise ratio, 40 s were used for each spectrum and 10 scans
179 were accumulated at 10% of the maximum power of the 514 nm laser, in the 1000-2000 cm⁻¹ spectral
180 window.

181 Deposition of carbonaceous material on the spent catalysts was quantified by Temperature
182 Programmed Hydrogenation (TPH) in a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 coupled to a Mass
183 Spectrometer (Pfeifer Vacuum OmniStar). Sample was first heated at 550 °C for 1 h, under a He
184 flow, and cooled down to ambient temperature. Then, a flow of 5% H_2 /Ar was passed through the
185 sample heated at 10 °C/min up to 950 °C and $m/z=15$ (CH_4) signal was recorded.

186 Nitrogen isotherms and XRD were carried out for samples reduced ex-situ in a tubular quartz reactor
187 at 600 °C for 1 h (heating rate 5 °C/min) in 50% H_2 -He flow (50 mL/min).

188 2.3. Catalytic test

189 The APR test of 10 wt.% glycerol in water (glycerol/water mole ratio 0.0217) synthetic mixture was
190 carried out in a fixed-bed up-flow reactor (internal diameter=5.1 mm; length=305 mm) made in
191 Hastelloy (Microactivity Effi, PID Eng&Tech). About 1.8 g of catalyst (particle size 0.04-0.16 mm)
192 was placed on a stainless steel frit, covered with a quartz wool plug, and then reduced under
193 10 % H_2 /He flow at 600 °C for 2 h (heating rate 5 °C/min) at atmospheric pressure. The reactor was
194 pressurised with He up to the desired pressure, then the He flow was switched to bypass and 0.02
195 mL/min of the liquid feedstream (pH 6.6) pumped into the reactor while the temperature was
196 progressively raised at 5 °C/min up to the reaction temperature. Catalytic tests were carried out at 260
197 °C and 50 bar at a WHSV of 0.68 h^{-1} (calculated as feed mass flow/catalyst mass) with a total duration
198 of 100 h. Zero time was taken when reactants reached the catalyst bed, once ensured the reaction
199 temperature was reached. The reaction products were cooled down to 5 °C and the gas and liquid
200 phases separated. The gas phase was passed through 100 mL mixing vessel in order to minimize the
201 pulses of gas products coming from the reactor, and analysed online every 30 min by a gas
202 chromatograph (μ GC Agilent), equipped with four parallel columns. The liquid fraction was
203 manually collected in 3 mL vials every 1 h, and then off-line analysed by either gas chromatography
204 (GC-FID Agilent, HP-WAX) and HPLC (Waters 616, Hi-Plex H column) equipped with Refraction
205 Index Detector. The total organic carbon (TOC) was measured off-line on a Shimadzu TOC-L
206 apparatus. Details about the gas and liquid product external calibration curves are given in the
207 Supporting Information file.

208 The total glycerol conversion (X_{Gly}), the carbon conversion to gas (X_{gas}), hydrogen selectivity (S_{H_2}),
209 hydrogen yield (Y_{H_2}), alkane selectivity ($S_{alkanes}$) and liquid products yield (Y_i) were calculated as
210 follows:

$$211 X_{Gly} (\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{Gly}^{in} - F_{Gly}^{out}}{F_{Gly}^{in}} \quad (2)$$

212 $F_{\text{Gly}}^{\text{in}}$ and $F_{\text{Gly}}^{\text{out}}$ are the molar flow of glycerol in the reactor inlet and outlet, respectively.

213
$$X_{\text{gas}} (\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{C}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{C,liq}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{C}}^{\text{in}}} \quad (3)$$

214 F_{C}^{in} is the carbon molar flow in the reactor inlet, and $F_{\text{C,liq}}^{\text{out}}$ is the carbon molar flow in the liquid
215 products.

216
$$S_{\text{H}_2} (\%) = 100 \times \frac{2 \cdot F_{\text{H}_2}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{H}}^{\text{gas}}} \quad (4)$$

217 $F_{\text{H}_2}^{\text{out}}$ and $F_{\text{H}}^{\text{gas}}$ are the molar flow of hydrogen and hydrogen atoms in gas products, respectively.

218
$$Y_{\text{H}_2} (\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{H}_2}^{\text{out}}}{7 \cdot F_{\text{Gly}}^{\text{in}}} \quad (5)$$

219
$$S_{\text{alkanes}} (\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{C,alkanes}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{C}}^{\text{gas}}} \quad (6)$$

220 $F_{\text{C,alkanes}}^{\text{out}}$ and $F_{\text{C}}^{\text{gas}}$ are the flow of carbon atoms in alkanes and in gas products, respectively.

221
$$Y_i (\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{C,i}}^{\text{out}}}{3 \cdot F_{\text{Gly}}^{\text{in}}} \quad (7)$$

222 where $F_{\text{C,i}}^{\text{out}}$ is the carbon molar flow in the liquid stream.

223 Additional experiments were carried out to evaluate the catalytic activity in the liquid phase WGS.
224 The experiments were performed at 260 °C and 50 bar in the same reaction setup. The catalyst (0.2
225 g) was pretreated as for APR experiments. Deionized liquid water (0.04 mL/min) was fed together
226 with pure CO (3.5 mL/min STP), which gave WHSV=12.0 h⁻¹ (based on the liquid feed) and
227 GHSV=1050 h⁻¹ (based on CO). The gaseous products were swept from the reactor by flowing 40
228 mL/min helium. The resulting H₂O/CO mole ratio was 15, which corresponds to the theoretical value
229 during APR process. Each run lasted 10 h, where stabilization was achieved after 5 h. The gas
230 products were analyzed on-line by μ GC. Conversion of CO and yields of CO₂ and CH₄ were
231 calculated as follows:

232
$$X_{\text{CO}} (\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{in}}} \quad (8)$$

233
$$Y_{i,WGS} (\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_i^{out}}{F_{CO}^{in}} \quad (9)$$

234 F_{CO}^{in} and F_{CO}^{out} are the molar flows of CO in the reactor inlet and outlet, respectively, and F_i^{out} is the
 235 molar flow of product (CO₂ or CH₄) in the reactor outlet.

236 2.4. Mass transfer limitations

237 The existence of internal and external mass transfer limitations, was checked by the Weisz-Prater
 238 (equation 10) and the Mears (equation 11) criterion, respectively

239
$$\Phi_{WP} = \frac{(r_{obs}) \cdot \rho_{cat} \cdot r_p^2}{D_{G-W,eff} \cdot C_{G,s}} \quad (10)$$

240
$$\frac{MR}{n} = \frac{(r_{obs}) \cdot \rho_{bed} \cdot r_p}{K_C \cdot C_{G,s}} < 0.15 \quad (11)$$

241 where (r_{obs}) is the observed reaction rate (mol/s·kg_{cat}); ρ_{cat} is the catalyst density (kg/m³); r_p is the
 242 catalyst particle radius (m); $D_{G-W,eff}$ is the effective diffusion coefficient of glycerol in water (m²/s);
 243 and $C_{G,s}$ is the glycerol concentration at the catalyst surface (mol/m³); ρ_{bed} is the packed bed density
 244 (kg/m³); k_C is the mass transfer coefficient (m/s); and n is the reaction order. Mass transfer coefficient
 245 was estimated using the Chilton-Colburn analogy and Wilson-Geankoplis correlation for liquid mass
 246 transfer at very low Reynolds numbers [23].

247 Typical values that ensure the absence of internal mass diffusion limitations are as follows: $\Phi_{WP} < 6$
 248 for a zero-order reaction; $\Phi_{WP} < 0.6$ for a first-order reaction; and $\Phi_{WP} < 0.3$ for a second-order
 249 reaction. In this work, Φ_{WP} and MR were calculated on the basis of the fastest reaction rate of
 250 $2.022 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/s·kg_{cat} (measured at the beginning of the reaction) and largest particle size with an
 251 effective diffusion coefficient of $1.45 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m²/s (estimated by Siddiqi-Lucas correlation, at 260 °C/50
 252 bar). Under the least favourable conditions, the obtained Φ_{WP} ($3.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$) and MR/n ($1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$) confirm
 253 that the performed experiments were conducted in the absence of both internal and external mass
 254 transport limitations.

255 3. Results and Discussion

256 3.1. Catalyst basic characterization

257 The investigated catalysts showed mesoporous characteristics (Figure 2) with specific surface area
 258 (S_{BET}) values ranging from 125 to 146 m²/g. After Pt loading into the CoAl spinel, surface area and
 259 pore volume size increased. S_{BET} increased up to 17%, being the highest at the lowest platinum

260 content. After reduction, S_{BET} values decreased at the expense of larger pores. Also, it was observed
261 that textural properties of the CoAl spinels were stabilised upon Pt loading. For instance, upon
262 reduction, S_{BET} of catalyst CoAl and xPt/CoAl samples decreased by around 19% and 10%,
263 respectively. Modification of the average pore size was also smaller in Pt loaded samples. Regarding
264 the alumina supported reference catalyst (0.3Pt/Al), it showed the smallest pores. For this sample,
265 both S_{BET} and pore size were preserved upon reduction.

266 TABLE 1

267 FIGURE 2

268 XRD patterns are shown in Figure 3. Independent of the support, none of the Pt-containing samples
269 showed any diffraction peak of platinum species, what pointed to a high Pt dispersion, as expected
270 by the low loadings applied ($1000 \times \text{Pt/Co mole ratio} = 2.3-7.7$). XRD pattern of catalyst CoAl matched
271 with the reference cobalt aluminate (PDF 00-044-0160) and cobalt oxide (PDF 00-042-1467) spinel.
272 xPt/CoAl samples showed similar diffraction spectrum to bare CoAl. However, after Pt loading, the
273 main diffraction peak slightly shifted to lower angles with a concomitant increase of the unit cell
274 (Table 1). The spinel crystallite size also increased from 5 nm to 6.3 nm. On the contrary, size of
275 metallic cobalt crystallite decreased by half. Catalyst 0.3Pt/Al showed characteristics peaks of γ -
276 alumina with a clear baseline elevation indicative of its amorphous nature. Moreover, in accordance
277 with previous characterisation data, its diffraction pattern was mimetic to the calcined counterpart.
278 Regarding the reduced xPt/CoAl samples, diffraction peaks of spinel phase remained (probably as
279 CoAl_2O_4) [7], and diffraction peaks of metallic Co arose, whereas any signal of Pt species was absent.

280 FIGURE 3

281 The local structure of the aluminium cations in the calcined catalysts was studied with solid-state ^{27}Al
282 NMR. The obtained spectra are displayed in Figure 4 and quantification results of Al^{3+} ions in
283 different coordination structures are shown in the inset table. Bare alumina presents three peaks at
284 7.5, 33.6 and 61.8 ppm, related to octahedral (Al_O), pentahedral (Al_P) and tetrahedral (Al_T) Al^{3+}
285 species, respectively [24]. CoAl spinel, however, showed only two peaks at 6.9 and 71.8 ppm,
286 strongly prevailing the octahedral symmetry ($\text{Al}_\text{O}/\text{Al}_\text{T} = 96/4$). Also, the low symmetry of the main
287 peak of CoAl indicated different Al^{3+} surrounding environments. The ^{27}Al NMR spectra of xPt/CoAl
288 samples revealed the existence of three Al^{3+} species (at 5.9, 33 and 61.7 ppm, respectively). Although
289 at a very low relative intensity (about 8% for both samples), the peak at around 33 ppm representing
290 Al^{3+} ions in unsaturated pentahedral coordination (Al_P) has emerged in the bimetallic samples, which
291 was not detected in bare CoAl. Data compiled in Figure 3 reflect that both bimetallic assays contained
292 relatively less amount of Al_O as compared to bare CoAl, suggesting that Pt ensembles anchor on these

293 sites. Also, in comparison to bare CoAl, Al_r and Al_o peaks of xPt/CoAl samples shifted to the right.
294 The higher the Pt loading, the higher the shift. These results clearly indicate that the deposition of
295 platinum ions caused changes in the distribution and coordination of Al_o sites of the cobalt aluminate
296 spinel.

297 FIGURE 4

298 The reducibility of the catalysts was studied by H₂-TPR (Figure 5). The reduction profile of 0.3Pt/Al
299 showed three very low intensity peaks. The peak at 227 °C was ascribed to the reduction of highly
300 dispersed platinum species with little interaction with the support, while the peak at 375 °C was
301 ascribed to the reduction of platinum species highly interacting with alumina [25]. The high
302 temperature peak, at around 660 °C, was related to reduction of alumina, assisted by hydrogen
303 spillover on Pt [26]. The reduction profile of CoAl sample showed four peaks. The low temperature
304 peaks, centred at 292 and 413 °C, were ascribed to the reduction of Co³⁺ to Co²⁺. Peak at 292 °C was
305 related to the surface cations without any interaction with the support, while peak at 413 °C was
306 ascribed to the reduction of Co³⁺ species in close interaction with the support. The huge peak centred
307 at 594 °C, was assigned to Co²⁺ reduction to Co⁰, and peak at 783 °C to the reduction of cobalt ions
308 in the cobalt aluminate (CoAl₂O₄) phase [7]. After Pt loading, a low temperature peak emerged, at
309 192 and 157 °C, for 0.3Pt/CoAl and 1Pt/CoAl, respectively. Quantification of these peaks is given in
310 Table 2. For both bimetallic samples, the hydrogen consumption of these peaks exceeded the
311 theoretical H₂ consumption of PtO_x species (PtO species were assumed), what suggested the
312 concomitant Co³⁺ to Co²⁺ reduction of free surface cations promoted by platinum, due to hydrogen
313 spillover from the Pt⁰ surface. As observed, the promotional effect was largest at the lowest Pt loading
314 (0.3 wt.%). For instance, at the lowest Pt loading, the reduction temperature of Co²⁺ to Co⁰ decreased
315 by around 31 °C, and that of cobalt ions in the spinel phase was reduced by around 47 °C. It should
316 be noted, however, that addition of Pt at 1 wt.% produced the opposite effect in the less reducible Co
317 species, as revealed by the increased reduction temperature of the Co²⁺ to Co (637 vs. 563 °C) and
318 that of Co ions in the spinel phase (820 vs. 736 °C). The cobalt reducibility at 600 °C varied from
319 62.6% for monometallic CoAl to 68.6% for 0.3Pt/CoAl (Table 2), indicating the promotional effect
320 of Pt. In conclusion, in the 0.3Pt/CoAl system reducibility of the metal species (Pt, Co) was
321 significantly promoted, as deduced from the increased low temperature hydrogen consumption, likely
322 due to a strong Pt-Co interaction. This is in line with the increased amount of available metallic Co
323 with respect to reference CoAl (Table 2). The smaller size of Co⁰ of the bimetallic samples, as
324 estimated by XRD, could be also involved. Also, available metallic Pt sites increased proportionally
325 to Pt loading. Thus, we hypothesize that Pt-Co interaction, especially at low Pt loadings, not only

326 promoted the reducibility of the catalyst but also increased the amount of available metallic Co
327 species.

328 TABLE 2

329 FIGURE 5

330 Regarding the density of acid sites of the reduced samples (Table 2), monometallic Pt sample showed
331 the lowest values ($0.34 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3}/\text{m}^2$) which was about 1.5-2 fold lower than that of Co-containing
332 samples. It was observed that among Co-containing samples, addition of Pt linearly increased the acid
333 sites density.

334 XPS measurements were carried out to investigate the surface composition and chemical valence
335 state of the active species. The binding energies (BE) of the Al, Co and Pt species and the surface
336 Co/Al atomic ratios are reported in Table 3. The Co 2p X-ray photoelectron spectra for the CoAl and
337 xPt/CoAl reduced samples are shown in Figure 6 (Al 2p and Pt 4d_{5/2} spectra are given in Figure S1,
338 Supplementary Information). The characteristic Co 2p doublet (Co 2p_{3/2} and Co 2p_{1/2}) due to spin-
339 orbit splitting was observed in all samples. The spectra were deconvoluted into Co⁰, Co²⁺ and shake
340 up satellites but no peaks were assigned to Co³⁺. The most interesting features were obtained from
341 the reduced assays. Al 2p level binding energy was measured at 74.2 eV, which is typically ascribed
342 to Al₂O₃ species. Co 2p peaks, in the xPt/CoAl system, shifted to higher binding energies in
343 comparison with CoAl catalyst. This reflected a charge transfer to adjacent electronegative Pt atoms
344 from slightly less electronegative Co, lowering electron density at the Co site [27]. Thus, supported
345 the above noted Pt-Co interaction in the investigated system. It is known that the Al 2p photoelectron
346 line of alumina can mask the most prominent photo-emitted electron of platinum (Pt 4f) [28].
347 However, in spite of the low platinum content, binding energies of the 4d_{5/2} level could be recorded
348 at 314.0 ± 0.2 eV for the bimetallic catalyst, what confirmed the existence of Pt⁰ phase.

349 TABLE 3

350 According to Table 3, the surface was enriched in Al ions (decrease in Co/Al evaluated by XPS) as
351 compared to bulk composition (evaluated by ICP-AES), what could be attributed to the lower surface
352 free energy of Al as compared to Co [29]. Moreover, Co/Al atomic ratio on surface decreased upon
353 reduction. This behaviour has been related to the incorporation of metallic species into the porous
354 structure [30], which would also explain the decrease in pore volume. Also, it is interesting to note
355 the higher Co/Al values measured for the bimetallic assays (as compared to parent CoAl) and,
356 regardless of their calcined or reduced state.

357 FIGURE 6

358 3.2. APR of glycerol

359 The activity of the prepared catalysts in the Aqueous-Phase Reforming was investigated using 10
360 wt.% glycerol/water feedstream. Two preliminary experiments (not shown) were carried out, first,
361 with no catalyst loaded into the reactor and second, with the reactor loaded with bare γ -alumina
362 (prepared by calcination in air at 500 °C for 4 h of aluminium(III) nitrate nonahydrate). Both runs
363 showed almost null activity, what reflected the critical role of the metallic function during the glycerol
364 conversion by APR (at the experimental conditions carried out in this work). Figure 7 shows the
365 evolution of glycerol total conversion (X_{Gly}) and carbon conversion to gas (X_{gas}) with TOS by the
366 investigated catalysts. The investigated catalysts proved high glycerol APR activity with a very high
367 conversion of glycerol (above 99%) during the whole test. Also, Pt-doped samples remained stable
368 throughout the entire test (100 h TOS) whereas CoAl suffered a weak deactivation at above 70 h
369 TOS. Indeed, the reported APR activity of the CoAl spinel supported catalysts can be deemed very
370 favourable as compared to data reported in literature [17,20].

371 **FIGURE 7**

372 Significant differences existed in the carbon conversion capability of the investigated catalysts.
373 Again, both Pt-Co bimetallic catalysts showed the highest and more stable carbon conversion to gas
374 (around 95%). Catalyst CoAl, with an initial X_{gas} value of 89.5% suffered 36% decay (X_{gas} of 57.3%
375 at 100 h TOS). Reference 0.3Pt/Al catalyst also displayed moderate decay in X_{gas} , from 95.9% at the
376 beginning of the reaction to 66.8% at 100 h TOS (30% decay). As previously noted, bimetallic
377 catalysts showed very stable operation over 100 h TOS, moreover, a subtle increase in X_{gas} was
378 appreciated. Overall, such stable performance in the glycerol conversion and gasification suggested
379 a relevant role of Pt species in catalyst stabilisation.

380 **TABLE 4**

381 For the sake of simplicity, the details of gaseous products and liquid products are given at 10 h and
382 100 h TOS, and can be found in Table 4 (the evolution with TOS for the complete run is shown in
383 Figure S2, Supporting Information). Hydrogen was the main gaseous product for all the tested
384 catalysts, with concentrations of around 60% by CoAl and 0.3Pt/Al, which dropped off to around
385 38% after incorporation of 1 wt.% Pt. Selectivity to hydrogen was also highest for these assays. CO₂
386 was the second most abundant gas product, throughout the whole reaction time. Light alkanes (mainly
387 methane) were formed in appreciable amounts, especially by the bimetallic catalysts. We believe such
388 product distribution might be due to factors such as: (i) the very low spatial velocity which enabled a
389 large contact time between catalyst and reactants, pushing forward the hydrogenation reactions of the
390 liquid intermediates, and (ii) the high reaction temperature employed in this work, where the CO
391 hydrogenation is thermodynamically and kinetically favoured [31]. According to reaction 3, the

392 theoretical H_2/CO_2 ratio for the glycerol APR is 7/3. Lower values indicated hydrogen was consumed
393 in parallel reactions (i.e. hydrogenation), while higher values indicated glycerol was partially
394 reformed, to yield intermediates that release hydrogen but hold carbon atoms in the skeleton. It was
395 observed that both monometallic samples gave the highest H_2/CO_2 values (> 2.4), while this ratio
396 decreased to 2.0 and 1.3, for 0.3Pt/CoAl and 1Pt/CoAl, respectively. This behaviour coincided with
397 their higher alkane production. It is likely that the small crystallites of cobalt particles and Pt-Co
398 alloying in the bimetallic samples was involved in such methane production [32]. This behaviour was
399 much more marked at the longest TOS ($S_{alkanes}$ 36-38% vs. 16%).

400 The yield to liquid product, evaluated as carbon moles in the liquid compounds ($F_{C,liq}$), was
401 significantly low under the investigated conditions (Table 4). These results agree with the high
402 conversion to gas achieved by these catalysts (Figure 7). It is worth pointing out the significantly
403 higher liquid flow rate obtained by monometallic catalysts (CoAl and 0.3Pt/Al) as compared to
404 bimetallic samples, reflecting the decisive role of catalyst formulation on product distribution.
405 Moreover, $F_{C,liq}$ varied with TOS, especially for monometallic assays, which showed three-fold
406 increase during the catalytic run, showing a clear trade-off with X_{gas} (Figure 7). Interestingly, $F_{C,liq}$
407 for bimetallic samples remained almost constant, as an evidence of its stability in the glycerol APR.

408 Liquid intermediates obtained by the cobalt-containing catalysts comprised mainly C3 (i.e. acetone,
409 propanols) compounds, what reflected a low decarbonylation activity. With respect to reaction
410 pathways, it seemed that Path II was predominant (Figure 1), which proceeded though glycerol
411 dehydration reaction over acid sites. The highest amount of C3 liquid intermediates was attained by
412 catalyst CoAl with the concomitant increase of the H_2/CO_2 ratio, at above theoretical values. CoAl
413 was the unique assay that contained propionic acid in the liquid stream, which is formed through the
414 dehydrogenation of 1-propanol and subsequent Cannizzaro reaction [33]. Regarding the reference
415 catalyst 0.3Pt/Al, it produced comparable yields of C2 and C3 products. The main liquid product of
416 the monometallic 0.3Pt/Al catalyst was ethanol, a secondary product obtained via the decarbonylation
417 of hydroxyacetone, and favoured by metallic function. Regarding the xPt/CoAl assays, at the lowest
418 Pt/Co ratio, yield to acetone dominated. As Pt loading increased, 2-propanol became the main liquid
419 compound, which was likely formed through the hydrogenation of acetone.

420 At high values of TOS the intensification of the dehydration route for both monometallic catalysts
421 was evidenced by an increased yield of liquid products ($F_{C,liq}$) with significantly higher selectivity to
422 propionic acid (CoAl) and ethanol (0.3Pt/Al). Gas phase product distribution also changed with TOS,
423 especially for the monometallic CoAl catalyst. This case, the selectivity to H_2 notably increased, up
424 to 86%. It is noteworthy that although X_{gas} declined with TOS for catalyst CoAl, the H_2 yield
425 increased (up to 89% for CoAl). However, for the monometallic catalyst 0.3Pt/Al selectivity to H_2

426 remained unchanged and thus, the H₂ yield decreased with TOS. Interestingly, bimetallic xPt/CoAl
427 system showed a more stable performance with TOS. For instance, yield to liquid products remained
428 at similar values, or even diminished. Concomitantly, the yield to H₂ increased to around 50%.

429 The obtained product distribution in APR experiments was hardly correlated with the surface acidity,
430 conceivably due to the small differences among them. Instead, it was suggested that the product
431 distribution depended on the balance between acid sites and metallic sites.

432 **3.3. Liquid phase WGS**

433 It is widely recognized that WGS reaction is a key step in the APR of polyols [9,34]. In order to gain
434 knowledge on the effect of Pt addition in the WGS activity of CoAl catalysts, additional experiments
435 were performed under the same conditions utilised in APR reaction, and at a water/CO mole ratio of
436 15/1 in the feedstream. Figure 8 displays data obtained at 10 h TOS (stability was achieved after 5 h
437 TOS). Interestingly, bare CoAl catalyst outperformed the WGS benchmark Pt catalyst [35,36], with
438 a CO conversion of around 51.2 and 29.9%, respectively. From Figure 8 it can be seen that WGS
439 activity of the bimetallic catalysts progressively increased with Pt loading, in line with previous
440 reports [11]. The promotional effect in WGS of Co-Pt alloys has been explained in terms of their
441 water dissociation ability and lowering of CO binding energy [37]. Also, data in Figure 8 reflected
442 that H₂ and CO₂ were the main products over all the assayed catalysts. Methanation activities were
443 very low, as follows: 0.3Pt/Al (0.3%) < 0.3Pt/CoAl (0.9%) < CoAl (1.5%) < 1Pt/CoAl (1.9%).
444 Indeed, under the investigated conditions, (i.e. feeding contained only CO/water), hydrogenation of
445 CO to methane was negligible, as due to the low availability of the in-situ produced hydrogen. Further
446 investigation should consider reaction conditions more representative of real APR operation to
447 elucidate whether high hydrogen availability could overcome such CO hydrogenation limitations.

448 **FIGURE 8**

449 **3.4. Characterization of spent catalysts**

450 Catalysts used in the APR of glycerol (100 h TOS) were thoroughly characterised in order to study
451 their stability. XRD diffractograms are displayed in Figure 3B. As occurred in the parent fresh
452 samples, no peaks of platinum were observed for any of the spent catalysts. Cobalt-containing
453 catalysts showed wide and asymmetric peaks, as in the fresh samples. From data summarised in Table
454 5 an increase of the spinel crystal size was observed, with a maximum increase of 38% measured for
455 catalyst CoAl. Characteristic peaks of metallic cobalt could be still detected, though, too weakly to
456 perform quantitative analysis. Also, boehmite phase was identified in both monometallic catalysts,
457 specially in sample 0.3Pt/Al. Indeed, the spinel structure can hinder the hydration of alumina to

458 bohemite. Taking into consideration that diffraction peaks of bohemite were not observed for the
459 bimetallic samples, it is likely that the presence of Pt could further inhibit the hydration. Also, it is
460 worth noting that only monometallic assays, and particularly catalyst CoAl, exhibited the
461 characteristic diffraction peak of carbon, at $2\theta = 25.5^\circ$.

462

TABLE 5

463 The textural properties of spent catalysts are shown in Figure 3, and summarised in Table 5. Catalyst
464 0.3Pt/Al suffered the most drastic alterations with around 70% decrease in the specific surface area
465 and pore volume. This behaviour was certainly ascribed to formation of bohemite [38]. CoAl spinel
466 showed the opposite behaviour with a substantial increment of its S_{BET} , likely aided by an important
467 reduction of the average pore size (from 11.8 to 7.6 nm) and minor decrease of its pore volume.
468 Finally, the bimetallic xPt/CoAl catalysts showed an intermediate behaviour. That is, both specific
469 surface area and pore volume decreased after usage, though moderately (within 6-14% decrease).
470 Pore size hardly varied, indicative of a higher textural and surface stability of bimetallic catalysts
471 compared to monometallic ones.

472 One of the most promising results of the investigated assays is their limited metal (Al, Co and Pt)
473 leaching (Table 5) even though the long run duration (100 h). The amount of Pt and Al leached out
474 from the fresh catalyst was less than 0.1% and 0.6%, respectively. Co leaching is an issue during the
475 aqueous phase reforming [37]. Our CoAl spinels leached restrained Co leaching with values in the
476 1.6 – 5.7% of the cobalt loaded. For instance, our results are more advantageous than those previously
477 reported in the literature with Co leaching of around 8.9% from carbon nanofiber supported catalysts
478 and during 24 h of ethylene glycol APR [39]. Thus, it is clear that the effectiveness of alternative
479 catalysts formulations requires a careful assessment in order to better anchor the metal.

480 From the H_2 -TPR profiles of the spent catalysts (Figure 5) some hydrogen consumption at below 600
481 °C was evidenced, what reflected that oxidation of the metal species (i.e. fresh catalysts were reduced
482 at 600 °C) occurred. As expected, 0.3Pt/Al was not oxidized. It is known that oxidation of Pt in
483 aqueous phase is difficult, even in the presence of hydrogen [40]. This was also supported by the fact
484 that the amount of available metal after APR was preserved for catalyst 0.3Pt/Al (Table 5). Taking
485 this into consideration, we have assumed that Pt-Co alloys were also resistant to oxidation under APR
486 conditions [37], thus, we hypothesize that the reduction peaks at below 600 °C were due to oxidized
487 cobalt species not interacting with Pt. The contribution of coke hydrogenation should not be
488 discarded, as suggested by the identification of carbonaceous deposits by Raman. Thus, the oxidation
489 percentages of Co given in Table 5 could be somewhat overestimated. Also, the reduction peak at
490 about 750 °C observed for all the cobalt containing samples, was ascribed to the reduction of cobalt
491 species in the $CoAl_2O_4$ spinel phase, not reduced by the reduction before the catalytic run.

492 Interestingly, bimetallic catalysts suffered less oxidation under APR conditions than the parent
493 monometallic CoAl. In quantitative terms, for the most favorable assay, the oxidation of cobalt
494 species was reduced by around 25% upon Pt doping (from 35.7 to 27.1%, for CoAl and 0.3Pt/CoAl,
495 respectively). This behavior was also consistent with the dramatic decrease in the exposed metal
496 atoms (95% decrease) of the former.

497

FIGURE 9

498 The nature of the above mentioned carbon deposits was investigated by Raman spectroscopy. The
499 Raman spectra (Figure 9) of both monometallic catalysts showed two bands (namely G and D). G
500 band (in the range 1594-1598 cm^{-1}) corresponded to ordered graphite-like structures while D band
501 (about 1342 cm^{-1}) was associated to the disordered carbon, generally amorphous carbon [41]. The
502 spectra of the spent bimetallic catalysts were quite different and showed very low intensity of both
503 bands, indicating negligible formation of carbonaceous deposits on the catalyst surface. It seemed
504 clear that the strong Pt-Co interaction inhibited the coke formation during APR of glycerol [42].
505 According to the ratio of intensity of D-Band to G-Band (I_D/I_G), it could be concluded that the
506 carbonaceous deposits on all the spent catalysts were predominantly amorphous, as I_D/I_G values were
507 above or near unity. In the case of CoAl catalysts, the amorphous carbon would coexist with graphitic
508 carbon, as suggested the diffraction peak at $2\theta = 25.5^\circ$. The absence of diffraction peaks of graphitic
509 carbon for bimetallic catalysts must be related to the low amount of deposits.

510

FIGURE 10

511 The carbonaceous deposits were quantified by TPH coupled to MS. Figure 10 shows the evolved
512 methane ($m/z=15$ signal) with temperature. Methane was formed from the hydrogenation of the
513 surface carbonaceous materials. The amount of surface carbon deposits ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{g}_{\text{cat}}$) are given in
514 Table 5. Methane was released in the 200-700 $^\circ\text{C}$ range. Such a wide temperature range suggested
515 the presence of different reactivity carbonaceous species, in agreement with the presence of two
516 Raman peaks. Low temperature peak (at around 200 $^\circ\text{C}$) can be ascribed to hydrogenation of the more
517 amorphous carbon, while the high temperature peak (between 500 and 600 $^\circ\text{C}$) was attributed to the
518 hydrogenation of more polymerized carbonaceous deposits that need higher temperatures for its
519 removal [43]. It is interesting to note that only Pt-containing assays showed the low temperature peak,
520 what suggests it could correspond to the hydrogenation of carbon deposited in the proximity of well
521 dispersed Pt centers, which could dissociate and spillover hydrogen on the surface and favour
522 hydrogenation of the carbonaceous precursor. Therefore, the high temperature peak was ascribed to
523 the hydrogenation of carbon deposits located in farthest positions from the metallic centers [44].
524 Notably, catalysts CoAl showed the largest methane yield, of around 13.5 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{g}_{\text{cat}}$. It was very

525 significant the attained reduction upon Pt loading, with around ten-fold decrease ($1.2\text{-}1.9\ \mu\text{mol}_C/\text{g}_{\text{cat}}$),
526 in line with previous XRD and Raman results.

527 **4. Conclusions**

528 We have investigated bare and Pt-impregnated cobalt aluminate catalysts for the activity and stability
529 in glycerol valorisation by Aqueous-Phase Reforming. The characterization of these samples revealed
530 that Pt loading stabilized the textural and structural properties of the CoAl spinel-supported catalysts.
531 In addition, at the lowest loading (i.e. 0.3%) Pt-Co interactions promoted the reduction and dispersion
532 of cobalt species. The investigated catalysts presented very high conversion of glycerol and
533 conversion to gas during the first 10 h TOS. This catalytic behaviour was sustained up to 100 h TOS
534 by the bimetallic catalysts. The incorporation of Pt to CoAl also increased methane production. Even
535 so, hydrogen was the main product for all the assayed catalysts, followed by CO_2 . The synergistic
536 effect between Pt and Co was also confirmed in the liquid phase WGS activity as bimetallic catalysts
537 showed higher activity than monometallic ones.

538 Examination of spent catalysts revealed that xPt/CoAl bimetallic catalysts preserved their structural
539 and textural properties, whereas APR conditions significantly deteriorated those of monometallic
540 ones. The total available metal atoms decreased considerably for catalysts without or with a lower
541 platinum content. H_2 -TPR confirmed the oxidation of metallic cobalt active centres, which was
542 probably the first step in leaching this metal. Amorphous carbonaceous deposits were detected by
543 Raman spectroscopy and quantified via methane formation using temperature-programmed
544 hydrogenation. Obtained results corroborated that Pt-containing catalysts formed less amount of
545 carbon deposits, as they could be hydrogenated by hydrogen spillover from Pt.

546 Largely, catalytic features of Pt-Co samples evidenced that bimetallic catalysts are suitable for
547 glycerol APR. However, and based on the presented results, further study should be carried out to
548 prevent cobalt oxidation and leaching.

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554

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672 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

673 Figure 1. Main reaction paths in glycerol APR (adapted from [7]).

674 Figure 2. Nitrogen isotherms (A) and pore size distribution (B) of the calcined, reduced (-r) and
675 spent (-u) samples.

676 Figure 3. (A) XRD patterns of the calcined and reduced (-r) samples; (B) spent (-u) samples.

677 Figure 4. ^{27}Al -NMR spectrum of calcined samples, and the distribution of differently coordinated
678 Al^{3+} sites (from the peak areas).

679 Figure 5. H_2 -TPR profiles for the fresh and spent (-u) samples.

680 Figure 6. Deconvoluted XPS spectra for Co 2p in reduced samples.

681 Figure 7. X_{Gly} (solid circles) and X_{gas} (open circles) evolution with TOS. Reaction conditions: 260
682 $^{\circ}\text{C}/50$ bar, 10 wt.% glycerol, $\text{WHSV}=0.68$ h $^{-1}$

683 Figure 8. CO conversion and products yield in liquid phase WGS reaction at TOS= 10 h.

684 Feedstream: $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}=15/1$ mole ratio.

685 Figure 9. Raman spectra of the spent catalysts.

686 Figure 10. TPH profiles of the spent catalysts.

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the catalysts.

Catalyst	Actual Pt ^a (wt.%)	S _{BET} (m ² /g) ^b	d _{pore} ^b (nm)	V _{pore} ^b (cm ³ /g)	d _{spinel} ^c (nm)	d _{Co} ^d (nm)	(311) peak 2θ position ^c (°)	Lattice parameter (nm) ^c
CoAl	0	125 (102)	6.8 (11.8)	0.28 (0.38)	5.0	14.7	37.06	0.8042 ±0.0014
0.3Pt/CoAl	0.29	146 (131)	12.7 (14.8)	0.56 (0.52)	6.3	6.9	37.04	0.8052 ±0.0011
1Pt/CoAl	1.09	139 (126)	12.8 (14.9)	0.54 (0.51)	6.3	6.5	36.99	0.8063 ±0.0006
0.3Pt/Al	0.36	138 (138)	3.9 (4.0)	0.19 (0.20)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.

^a from ICP-AES.

^b from nitrogen isotherms. In parenthesis, values for the reduced samples.

^c from XRD of the calcined samples.

^d metallic cobalt size from XRD of the reduced samples.

Table 2. H₂-TPR, H₂ chemisorption and surface acidity data.

Catalyst	Total H ₂ uptake (mmolH ₂ /g)	Low temperature peak H ₂ uptake (mmolH ₂ /g)	Degree of reduction ^a (%)	Exposed Pt ⁰ ^b (at.Pt/g _{cat})	Exposed Co ⁰ ^b (at.Co/g _{cat})	Surface acid sites density ^c (μmolNH ₃ /m ²)
CoAl	7.04	n.a.	62.6	0	23.0 · 10 ¹⁸	0.51
0.3Pt/CoAl	7.29	0.516 (0.0149)	68.6	5.2 · 10 ¹⁸	30.4 · 10 ¹⁸	0.56
1Pt/CoAl	7.36	0.659 (0.0559)	65.3	20.7 · 10 ¹⁸	25.5 · 10 ¹⁸	0.68
0.3Pt/Al	0.35	0.0195 (0.0185)	n.d.	6.9 · 10 ¹⁸	0	0.34

In parenthesis the theoretic amount assuming PtO species.

^a H₂ consumption at 600°C with respect to 950 °C (theoretical consumption ascribed to PtO subtracted); ^b from H₂ pulse chemisorption; ^c from ammonia mass gain.

Table 3. Results from XPS analysis.

Catalyst	Al 2p (eV)	Co 2p _{3/2} (eV)		Pt 4d _{5/2} (eV)		Surface Co/Al ^a	Bulk Co/Al ^b
		Co ²⁺	Co ⁰	Pt ²⁺	Pt ⁰		
CoAl	75.6 (74.2)	781.6 (781.3)	n.d. (778.0)	n.a.	n.a.	0.266 (0.139)	0.634
0.3Pt/CoAl	74.2 (74.2)	781.1 (781.6)	n.d. (778.2)	316.8 (n.d.)	n.d. (314.0)	0.271 (0.184)	0.633
1Pt/CoAl	74.2 (74.2)	781.2 (781.5)	n.d. (778.2)	317.7 (n.d.)	n.d. (314.2)	0.271 (0.186)	0.623
0.3Pt/Al	74.0 (73.5)	n.d.	n.d.	315.5 (n.d.)	n.d. (313.8)	n.d.	n.d.

Values in parenthesis for reduced samples.

^a from XPS of calcined samples; ^b from ICP-AES.

Table 4. Gaseous and liquid products characteristics at 10 h/100 h TOS. Reaction conditions: 260 °C/50 bar, 10 wt.% glycerol, WHSV=0.68 h⁻¹.

Catalyst	Gas products					Liquid products				
	S _{H2} (%)	S _{alkanes} (%)	Y _{H2} (%)	[H ₂] (%)	H ₂ /CO ₂	Y _{ethanol} (%)	Y _{acetone} (%)	Y _{propanols} (%)	Y _{propionic acid} (%)	F _{C,liq} (μmolC/min)
CoAl	67/86	29/16	55/89	61/78	2.8/4.7	0.2/0	2.8/2.6	2.5/1.9	5.5/13.8	9.0/28.4
0.3Pt/CoAl	49/53	34/38	37/44	50/52	2.0/2.0	0/0	1.1/0.9	0.5/0.4	0/0	3.5/1.3
1Pt/CoAl	32/49	40/36	21/36	37/49	1.8/1.8	0/0	0.6/0.4	3.4/2.7	0/0	4.3/3.3
0.3Pt/Al	65/65	31/29	57/46	60/62	2.7/2.8	1.4/4.1	0.9/1.0	0.7/1.7	0/0	8.8/22.1

The carbon balance was above 97% for all the experiments.

Table 5. Some characteristics of the spent catalysts.

Catalyst	S_{BET} (m^2/g)	V_{Pore} (cm^3/g)	d_{pore} (nm)	d_{spinel} (nm) ^a	Leached metals (wt.%)			Surface total metal ($\text{at.}_{(\text{Pt}+\text{Co})}/\text{g}_{\text{cat}}$)	Total H_2 uptake ($\text{mmol}_{\text{H}_2}/\text{g}$)	% oxidized (Co species) ^b	Carbon deposits ($\mu\text{mol}_{\text{C}}/\text{g}_{\text{cat}}$) ^c
					Al	Co	Pt				
CoAl	142 (102)	0.309 (0.375)	7.6 (11.8)	6.9 (5.0)	0.6	2.7	n.a	$1.1 \cdot 10^{18}$ ($23 \cdot 10^{18}$)	3.07	35.7	13.5
0.3Pt/CoAl	113 (131)	0.457 (0.521)	13.5 (14.8)	7.8 (6.3)	0.3	1.6	0.1	$6.4 \cdot 10^{18}$ ($35.6 \cdot 10^{18}$)	4.37	27.1	1.9
1Pt/CoAl	113 (126)	0.485 (0.514)	14.5 (14.9)	7.2 (6.3)	0.1	5.7	0.06	$40 \cdot 10^{18}$ ($46.2 \cdot 10^{18}$)	5.02	29.6	1.2
0.3Pt/Al	43 (138)	0.093 (0.198)	7.7 (4.0)	n.d.	0.4	n.a	0.02	$6.5 \cdot 10^{18}$ ($6.9 \cdot 10^{18}$)	0	n.a.	2.7

Values in parentheses for reduced non-used samples.

^a from XRD. ^b from TPR up to 600 °C. ^c from TPH.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

FIGURE 8

FIGURE 9

FIGURE 10

Supporting Information

Highly stable Pt/CoAl₂O₄ catalysts in Aqueous-Phase Reforming of glycerol

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1.1 Calibration of gas and liquid compounds

Gas compound	R²	Equipment
Helium	0.999959	μGC (channel 1)
Hydrogen	0.997904	μGC (channel 1)
Nitrogen	0.998172	μGC (channel 2)
Methane	0.997753	μGC (channel 2)
Carbon monoxide	0.999399	μGC (channel 2)
Carbon dioxide	0.998006	μGC (channel 3)
Ethylene	0.998277	μGC (channel 3)
Ethane	0.999624	μGC (channel 3)
Propane	0.955711	μGC (channel 4)
Propylene	0.995271	μGC (channel 4)
n-Butane	0.998724	μGC (channel 4)

Channel 1: column (Molecular sieve (MS5A HI), carrier Ar
Channel 2: column (Molecular sieve (MS5A HI)), carrier He
Channel 3: column (Poraplot (PPQ)), carrier He
Channel 4: column (Al₂O₃-KCl), carrier He

Liquid compound	R²	Equipment
Glycerol	0.9985	HPLC
1-Propanol	0.9961	GC-FID
2-Propanol	0.9895	GC-FID
Acetaldehyde	0.9872	GC-FID
Acetic acid	0.9928	GC-FID
Acetone	0.9999	GC-FID
Ethanol	0.9995	GC-FID
Ethylene glycol	0.9990	GC-FID
Hydroxyacetone	0.9997	GC-FID
Methanol	0.9998	GC-FID
Propionic acid	0.9935	GC-FID
Propylene glycol	0.9978	GC-FID

HPLC: column (Hi-Plex H)
GC-FID: column (HP-WAX), carrier He

1.2 XPS spectra for Al 2p and Pt 4d_{5/2} in reduced samples

Figure S1. XPS spectrum of Al 2p (A) and Pt 4d_{5/2} (B) in the reduced samples.

1.3 TOS evolution of gas products and liquid products.

Figure S2. Evolution with TOS of (A) main compounds of the gas phase and (B) liquid products yield. Reaction conditions: 260 °C/50 bar, 10 wt.% glycerol, WHSV=0.68 h⁻¹